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HATE CRIME

Politico-Legal Dimension of Hate Speech

*Girjesh Shukla**

Social conflicts are common phenomenon in every society. But these are more pronounced in a pluralistic society like India characterised by different cultural, religious, ethnic, lingual groups. Social conflicts contribute to the growth and development of the society and thus are desirable to that extent. But these are detrimental to the societal health when threaten peace and harmony in the society.¹

There is a class of offences against public tranquillity in which no actual force is employed or displayed, but in which some steps are taken which tend to cause disturbance in the society. These include formation of secret societies, seditious conspiracies, libels or *words spoken*,² which often cause discord in the society. One such violent expression of socio-political conflict is hate speeches. Such tactics are not new to our political history though it has witnessed a surprising upsurge during recent past.³

The pre-censorship is not recommended against hate speech. The post censorship or punishment for hate speeches even though are not true answers against hate speech as the harm would be inflicted, but are recommended to mitigate against hate speech.

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¹ No democratic society advocates instigation of violence by any individual or group of individuals based on political, religious, linguistic or regional ideologies. It affects the public peace and tranquillity. Unlawful assemblies, riots, insurrection, rebellions are examples of this nature. All of them have one common feature, namely, that the normal tranquillity of society is disturbed either by actual force or at least by the show and threat of it.

² Stephen's Criminal Law of England (Vol. II) pp. 242-44

³ The recent Gujrat election was basically dominated by the slogan "Jeetega Gujrat" and then a slogan with violence by political outfits, "Mumbai for Mumbaikars" in Maharastra or violence against migrated tea workers in Assam. See also the group-conflicts between 'Saccha Sauda' of Baba Ram Rahim and Sikh community.

It would be pertinent to discuss hate speeches *vis-à-vis* freedom of speech and expression.⁴ This work also seeks to analyse politico-legal and constitutional dimensions of hate speech. Hate speech remains a species of speech and unless it can be brought under legal sanctions, it would enjoy right under freedom of speech and expression under Article 19 of the Constitution.

Conceptualizing Hate Speech

Hate speech is a species of hate crimes, i.e., a criminal manifestation of prejudice.⁵ They may be distinguished from parallel crimes⁶ in terms of the mental state of the actor as well as the nature of the harm caused. A parallel crime may be motivated by any number of factors whereas bias crimes are motivated by a specific, personal and group-based reason; the victim's real or perceived membership in a particular group.⁷

Hate speech is "designed to promote hatred on the basis of race, religion, ethnicity, or national origin."⁸ It is a tool to disseminate the idea of racial or otherwise superiority, to incite violence, and to reinforce stereotypes. It may be used to get political support from particular section of society on the basis of language,⁹ caste, community or religion.¹⁰ It is inappropriate to associate hate speech only with religion as there are other aspects of such speech including economic motive.

Indian Constitution and Freedom of Speech

The freedom of speech and expression is one of the most valuable rights guaranteed to a citizens of India by the Constitution and has been jealously guarded by the courts. Free political discussion is deemed essential for the proper functioning of a democratic government.

⁴ Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution of India

⁵ Hurd, Heidi and Michael S. Moore, "Punishing Hatred and Prejudice" in 56 Stan L Rev 1081 (2004), pp. 1128-29

⁶ Crimes are similar in every manner but for the absence of bias motivation.

⁷ *Ibid*

⁸ Michael Rosenfeld, "Hate Speech in Constitutional Jurisprudence: A Comparative Analysis" 24 Cardozo L. Rev. 1523 (2003) (Demonstrating International and domestic reaction to hate speech)

⁹ *Jagdev Singh Sidhanti v Pratap Singh* AIR 1965 SC 183

¹⁰ This ground is basically alleged against Bhartiya Janta Party (BJP). See the alleged speeches of BJP leaders at an election rally in Maharashtra as Cited by supreme court in *Manohar Joshi v. Nitin Bhaurao Patil* (1996) 1 SCC 169. see also *Ramakant Mayekar v. Smt. Celine D'Silva* AIR 1996 SC 826 & *Prof. Ramchandra G. Kapse v Haribansh Ramakbal Singh* AIR 1996 SC 817

In "Civil liberties and Human Rights" David Feldman,¹¹ counted certain justifications for and limits of freedom of expression. *Firstly*, self-expression is a significant instrument of freedom of conscience and self-fulfilment. *Secondly*, freedom of expression enables people to contribute to debates about social and moral values. The best way to find the best or truest theory or model of anything is to permit the widest possible range of ideas to circulate. *Thirdly*, the freedom of expression allows political discourse which is necessary in any country which aspires to be democratic. And *lastly*, it facilitates artistic scholarly endeavours of all sorts.

In *Indian Express Newspapers (Bombay) Pvt. Ltd. v Union of India*,¹² the Supreme Court delineated four broad social purposes of freedom of speech and expression; *Firstly*, it helps an individual to attain self fulfilment, *Secondly* it assists in the discovery of truth; *thirdly*, it strengthens the capacity of an individual in participating in decision-making and *lastly*, it provides a mechanism by which it would be possible to establish a reasonable balance between stability and social change.

The court observed that all members of the society should be able to form their own beliefs and communicate them freely to others. Freedom of speech and expression should, therefore, receive a generous support from all those who believe in the participation of people in the administration.

Restrictions on Freedom of Speech

The Constitution has placed restrictions on freedom of speech and expression to protect and promote orderly society and human values. Under Article 19(2), there are three¹³ grounds for curbing hate speeches. These are *law and order* which includes incitement to the offences, *public order* and *security of state*. But as it is an inoperative clause, legislation is needed to declare 'hate speech' a crime.

It is necessary that the law imposing restrictions must be reasonable¹⁴ and in deciding the reasonableness of restrictions the courts should consider the *nature of the right* alleged to have been infringed, the underlying purpose of the restrictions imposed, the disproportion of the

¹¹ Cited in *Secretary, Ministry of I. & B. v Cricket Association, Bengal AIR 1995 SC 1236*

¹² (1985) 1 SCC 641 : AIR 1986 SC 515 cited in *Secretary, Ministry of I. & B. v Cricket Association., Bengal AIR 1995 SC 1236*.

¹³

¹⁴ Article 19(2) of the Constitution

imposition and the prevailing conditions including the social values whose needs are sought to be satisfied by means of the restrictions.

In *S. Rangarajan* case¹⁵ court observed "freedom of speech is subject to reasonable restriction in the larger interest of the community and the country set out in Article 19 (2). These restrictions are intended to strike a proper balance between the liberty guaranteed and the social interests specified in Article 19(2)."¹⁶ Thus, there should be a compromise between freedom of expression and social interests. The court cannot simply balance the two interests as if they are of equal weight.

Restriction on Hate Speech; Clear and Present Danger Test

Every instigating or alarming speech does not come under restriction clause under Article 19(2). The issue in every case is whether the words used are used in such circumstances and are of such a nature as to create a *clear and present danger*; that they will bring about substantive evils which the Centre or state legislatures have a right to prevent; it is a question of proximity and degree.

It is difficult to determine as to when the right of free speech becomes injudicious. For the analysis of the three expressions used in article 19(2) i.e. law and order, public order and security of state, one has to imagine three concentric circles. Law and order represents the largest circle within which is the next circle representing public order and the smallest circle represents the security of the State. All cases of disturbances of public tranquillity fall in the largest circle but some of them are outside 'public order' for the purpose of the phrase 'maintenance of public order', similarly every breach of public order is not necessarily a case of an act likely to endanger the security of the State.¹⁷

Adopting this test it may be stated that state is at the centre and society surrounds it. Disturbances of society go in a broad spectrum from mere disturbance of normal life to jeopardy of the State. The acts become graver and graver as we journey from the periphery of the larger circle towards the centre. In this journey we travel first through public tranquillity; then through public order and lastly to the security of the

¹⁵ *S. Rangarajan v P. Jagjivan Ram* (1989) 2 SCC 574

¹⁶ This is the difference between the First Amendment to the U.S. Constitution and Article 19 of our Constitution except the broad principles and purpose of guarantee. See also; *Secretary, Ministry of I.& B. v Cricket Association., Bengal* AIR 1995 SC 1236. For US cases See, *Mutual Film Corporation v. Industrial Commission* (1914) 236 US 230, *Burstyan v Wilson* (1951) 343 US 495 and *Schenck v United States* (1918) 249 US 47.

¹⁷ *Ram Manohar Lohia v State of Bihar* AIR 1966 SC 740

State. It is the last two, i.e., public order and security of State which attract restrictions.

Hate Speech and Legislative Trends

Hate speech is designed to promote hatred on the basis of race, religion, ethnicity, or national origin.¹⁸ In traditional offences, the offender is guilty only when *criminal act*, commission or omission occurs with a simultaneous *mens rea* or criminal intent. Such elements would be the basic requirements for criminalizing such hate speeches also.

Indian Penal Code, 1860

Indian Penal Code (IPC) has certain provisions prohibiting incitement, abetment, and connivance and conspiring criminal activities in general. Section 153 deals with a somewhat *diffused offence* which is neither abetment nor promotion of rioting. It is provocation of a person to commit rioting by malignant or wanton doing of an illegal act. A person who appeals to other person's sense of honour or wounded pride may¹⁹ or may not²⁰ be guilty of an offence under this section.²¹ This section will apply when there is "doing any thing which is illegal"²² Moreover it must have been done *malignantly or wantonly*²³ and with intention or knowledge that it will probably provoke a 'breach of peace'.²⁴ The accused may be punished under this section if his act of provocation is sufficient for rioting. In other words, offence will be judged upon the temper and feeling of the person subjected to the provocation and its knowledge by the accused.²⁵

S. 153A provides for punishment for promoting enmity between different groups on grounds of religion, race, place of birth, residence, language, caste or community or any other like ground whatsoever or bringing about disharmony or feeling of hatred or ill-will between different religious, racial, language or regional groups or castes or communities. It is only where the written or spoken words have the tendency or intention of creating public disorder or disturbance of law

¹⁸ Michael Rosenfeld, *op.cit.*

¹⁹ *Kahanji*, I.L.R. 18 Bom. 758

²⁰ *Hussain Baksh*, I.L.R. 27 All. 569

²¹ Dr. Hari Singh Gour "Penal law of India" edition XI vol. II (2001), Law Pub. (India), Pvt. Ltd. P.1445

²² *Jasmani v. Emperor* AIR 1936 All. 534 at p. 535

²³ Law commission of India suggested for deletion of these words as being imprecise and without any purpose. The commission also suggested for enhanced punishment. See Law Commission of India 42nd Report, 1971.

²⁴ Dr. Hari Singh Gaur, *op. cit.*, p 1446

²⁵ *Ibid*

and order or affect public tranquillity that the law needs to step in to prevent such an activity. The intention to cause disorder or incite people to violence is the *sine qua non* of the offence under s. 153A, and prosecution has to prove the existence of *mens rea* in order to succeed. If these incitements and hatred are very much casual in nature and less frequent then person may not be punished under this section.²⁶

S. 153A covers a case where a person by "words, either spoken or written, or by signs or by visible representations" promotes or attempts to promote such feeling. It is seen that s. 153A(1)(a) is not confined to the promotion of feelings of enmity etc. on grounds of religion only but also takes in promotion of such feelings on other grounds as well such as race, place of birth, residence, language, caste or community.²⁷

The s. 153B is supplementary to existing provisions like s. 153A and 295A of IPC, which provides for taking action against individuals for activities promoting enmity or prejudicial to the maintenance of harmony between different groups on ground of religion, place of birth, race, caste and residence. Similarly, s. 505(2), of IPC makes any statement punishable which is made with a view to create or promote enmity, hatred or ill-will between classes of the society. The main distinction between the two offences is that while publication of the

²⁶ *Balwant Singh v. State of Punjab* AIR 1995 SC 1785 para 9, where the accused raised the following slogans :

"1. Kalistan Zindabad.

2. Raj Karega Khalsa, and.....!

3. Hinduan Nun Punjab Chon Kadh Ke Chhadange, Hun Mauka Aya Hai Raj Kayam Karan Da." The Supreme Court found that raising three casual slogans may not be sufficient to prove the prosecution version.

²⁷ *Babu Rao Patel v. State (Delhi Administration)* AIR 1980 SC 763 para. referred to Muslims generally as 'a basically violent race' and went on to say 'communalism is, therefore, an instrument of a minority with a racial tradition of rape, loot, violence and murder as is found in India with a Muslim population of 12.7%. In Pakistan the Hindu minority is 6.6% but because its racial tradition is different it does not indulge in communal riots..... Three essentials are necessary for violent communalism. The community must be a minority, the minority must be sizeable and the minority must have a tradition of murder and violence.... We find these three essentials in the Muslim community of India'. He then stated in the article that in Pakistan and particularly in East Bengal peace loving and terror struck Hindu minority was being eliminated by periodical killing and conversions on a mass scale. 'Young Hindu males were compelled to undergo vasectomy operations, young and pretty Hindu girls became the victims of Islamic beds of lust'. It is then said 'it is not in the nature and religion of the Hindu of India to be intolerant and blood-thirsty like the followers of Islam'. According to him the only answer to the problem of communalism was to declare India a Hindu State.

words or representation is not necessary under the former, such publication is *sine qua non* under s. 505.²⁸

The common feature in both sections being promotion of feeling of enmity, hatred or ill-will "between different" religious or racial or language or regional groups or castes and communities it is necessary that at least two such groups or communities should be involved. Merely inciting the feeling of one community or group without any reference to any other community or group cannot attract either of the two sections.²⁹

Chapter XV of IPC deals with certain offences against religion. These offences include injuring or defiling places of worship with intent to insult the religion of any class³⁰, deliberate and malicious act intended to outrage religious feeling of any class by insulting its religion or religious belief³¹, disturbing religious assembly³², trespassing on burial places³³ and uttering words etc. with deliberate intent to wound religious feelings.³⁴ For the topic at hand, s. 295A and 298 are important.

S. 295A has been intended to respect the religious susceptibility of persons of different religious persuasion or creeds.³⁵ This section envisages the essential ingredients of the punishment and provides that whoever, with deliberate and malicious intention of outraging the religious feelings of any class of citizens of India, by words, either spoken or written, or by signs or by visible representations or otherwise, insults or attempts to insult the religion or the religious beliefs of that class, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both. It is pertinent to note that an act may be deliberate without being malicious and it may be malicious without being deliberate, since it may be reckless without being intentional. What is required to constitute the offence is the presence of both.³⁶

S. 295A does not penalise any and every act of insult or attempt to insult the religion or the religious beliefs of a class of citizens, which are perpetrated with the deliberate and malicious intention of outraging the religious feelings of that class. Insults to religion offered unwittingly or

²⁸ *Bilal Ahmed Kaloo v. State of A.P* AIR 1997 SC 3483

²⁹ *Id.* para 11

³⁰ Section 295 of IPC 1960

³¹ *Id.*, Section 295A

³² *Id.*, Section 296

³³ *Id.*, Section 297

³⁴ *Id.*, Section 298

³⁵ *Dr. Hari Singh Gour, op.cit.*, p. 2334

³⁶ *King v Naga Shwe* AIR 1939 Rang. 199 at p. 200 cited by *Gour, op.cit.*, p. 2336

carelessly or without any deliberate or malicious intention to outrage the religious feelings of that class, do not come within the section. It only punishes the aggravated form of insult to religion when it is perpetrated with the deliberate and malicious intention of outraging the religious feelings of that class.

Similarly, s. 298 of IPC also prohibits uttering of any word with deliberate intent to wound religious feelings. The main objective of this section is to allow all fair altitude to religious discussion and on other hand to prevent any religion from offering, under the pretext of such discussion, intentional insult to what is sacred to others.³⁷ It is therefore obvious that s. 298 relates to the oral words uttered in the presence of a person with the intention of wounding his religious feelings and probably therefore it may not have any application in cases when grievance relates to written article.³⁸

It is interesting that scope of 295A and 298 is overlapping. Amongst the offences under the two sections the offence under former is more serious than later.³⁹ 'Outraging' is stronger than 'wounding'. In order to bring a case within ambit of 295A it is not the matter of discourse as the manner of it. The words used should be such as are bound to be regarded by any reasonable person intended to outrage the feelings of any class of citizens of India.

Provisions under Representation of People Act, 1951

S. 123 of the Representation of People Act 1951 (R. P. Act) prohibits the promotion of feeling of enmity or hatred between different classes of citizens of India on the grounds of religion, race, caste, community or language by a candidate or his agent or any other person with the consent of the candidate or for prejudicially affecting the election of any candidate or any attempt thereof.⁴⁰ Any such act or attempt will be deemed to constitute corrupt practice.⁴¹ Accordingly a speech-related corrupt practice may be either of two; first, the appeal for vote on the

³⁷ Dr. Hari Singh Gaur, *op.cit.*, p. 2352

³⁸ *Shalibhodra shah v Swami Krishna Bharti*, 1981 Cr.L.J. 113, at p. 116 (Guj.)

³⁹ Dr. Hari Singh Gaur, *op.cit.*, p. 2337

⁴⁰ Section 123(3A) of Representation of Peoples Act 1951

⁴¹ To which activity does the language of corrupt practice apply? In America the statutory invocation of the term corruption in the regulatory context of campaign behaviour has only one meaning, i.e., the improper use of money to secure electoral advantage. [G. J. Jacobsohn, 'Wheels of Secularism' Oxford (2002), p. 164]. However in our country it includes not only the money and political irregularities but also covers the inappropriate use of speech to advance electoral advantage.

basis of religion, caste, creed or language; and second, the promotion of feeling of enmity or hatred between class of citizens.

Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973

S. 144 of CrPC makes certain provisions regarding hate speech. It finds place in Chapter XI under the heading "Temporary Orders in urgent cases of nuisance or apprehended damage". The section confers powers to issue an order at once in urgent cases of nuisance or '*apprehended danger*'. Such orders may be made by Magistrates when there is sufficient ground for proceeding and immediate prevention or speedy remedy is desirable. The grounds for making the order are that in the opinion of the Magistrate such direction is likely to prevent, or tends to prevent obstruction, annoyance or injury, to any person lawfully employed or danger to human life, health or safety or a disturbance of the public tranquillity or a riot⁴² or an affray.⁴³

The gist of action under s. 144 is the urgency of the situation and its efficacy in the likelihood of being able to prevent some harmful occurrences. It is used in a judicial manner and subject to further judicial scrutiny. There is no general proposition that an order under s. 144, Criminal Procedure Code cannot be passed without taking evidence.⁴⁴

The Chapter VIII of the Criminal Procedure Code has an explanatory heading 'Prevention of Offences' for the prevention of crimes and disturbances of public tranquillity and breaches of the peace. Division A of this chapter is for security for keeping the peace on conviction. Division B then consists of 12 sections⁴⁵ including provisions for taking security for keeping the peace; good behaviour from persons disseminating sedition, vagrants and suspected persons and habitual offenders. These provisions enable Magistrates to make an order to show-cause and execute a bond, with or without sureties for keeping the peace for certain period not exceeding one year. This is an instance of *preventive justice* which the courts are intended to administer. This provision like the preceding one is in aid of orderly society and *seeks to nip in the bud the conduct subversive of the peace and public tranquillity.*

⁴² S. 146 of IPC

⁴³ S. 159 of IPC

⁴⁴ *Mst. Jagrupa Kumari v Chotay Narain Singh*, (1936) 37 Cri LJ 95 (Pat.). Supreme Court approved this observation in the above case.

⁴⁵ Ss. 107-110 and 112-119 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973

Freedom of Speech, Hate Speech and Judicial Trends

Courts in India have history of securing freedom of speech and expression, even going beyond the doctrinaire sense of permissible limitations laid under the Constitution itself.

There can be no doubt that freedom of speech and expression includes freedom of propagation of ideas,⁴⁶ but individual has no such right of propagation of his idea when it is squarely coming in the domain of threat to security of state, public order or incitement of an offence.⁴⁷

The State can restrict freedom of speech and expression provided under Article 19(2) but this can be done only on the grounds mentioned in this clause. Any restriction imposed by State through legislations have always been scrutinised by the courts on the basis of 'clear and present danger' test.

Initially, security of state and incitement of offences were considered to be grounds for restricting freedom of speech and expression.⁴⁸ However this narrow approach was avoided by amendment in the constitution and 'public order' has been inserted in Article 19(2) as a separate ground.⁴⁹

⁴⁶ Patanjali Sastri J, *Romesh Thappar v State of Madras* AIR 1950 SC 124, para 6

⁴⁷ In the classification of offences in the Penal Code, for instance, VI lists waging war against the Queen (S. 121), sedition (S. 124-A) etc. as "offences against the state", because they are calculated to undermine or affect the security of the state, and Chap. VIII defines "offences against the public tranquillity" which include Unlawful Assembly (S. 141), Rioting (S. 146,) Promoting enmity between classes (S. 158A), Affray (S. 159) etc.

⁴⁸ In this category only those offences against public order which aim at undermining the security of the State or overthrowing it, have been justified as a ground for restricting freedom of speech. Nothing less than endangering the foundations of the State or threatening to overthrow it could justify curtailment of the right of freedom of speech and expression [*Romesh Thaper v State of Madras* AIR 1950 SC 124; *State of Bihar v Shailbala Devi* AIR 1952 SC 329].

According to *Romesh Thaper's* case, a line to be drawn in the field of public order or tranquillity marking off, more or less roughly, the boundary between those serious and aggravated forms of public disorder which are calculated to endanger the security of the State and the relatively minor breaches of the peace of a purely local significance and thus treating the differences in degree as if they were different in kind for this purpose.

Thus, very narrow and stringent limits have been set to permissible legislative abridgement of the right of free speech and expression and this was doubtless due to the realisation that freedom of speech and of the press lay at the foundation of all democratic organisations, for without free political discussion no public education, so essential for the proper functioning of the processes of popular Government, is possible. *A freedom of such amplitude might involve risks of an abuse.*

⁴⁹ Constitution (First Amendment) Act, 1951

This widening of ground of restriction was explained in *Superintendent Central Prison v Ram Manohar Lohia*.⁵⁰ The Court observed:

'Public order' and 'public safety' are allied matters... it seems best to analyse the opposite concepts... respectively labelled as 'public disorder' and public unsafety'. If 'public safety' is, as we have seen equivalent to 'security of the State', what one may have designated as public unsafety may be regarded as equivalent to 'insecurity of the State'. When we approach the matter in this way, we find that while 'public disorder' is wide enough to cover a small riot as an affray and other cases where peace is disturbed by or affects a small group of persons, 'public unsafety' (or 'insecurity of the State') will usually be connected with serious internal disorders and such disturbances of public tranquillity it jeopardize the security of the State. Thus 'public order' may well be paraphrased in the context as public tranquillity and the words 'public safety' and 'public order' may be read as equivalent to "security of the State" and "public tranquillity."

Thus the court widened the net of restriction through this interpretation. State may, in interest of public order prohibit and punish whereby breach of peace is likely to be caused.

It is alarming is that court seems much cautious while dealing with hate crimes. For example, as discussed earlier, while acquitting the accused in *Superintendent Central Prison* case, Supreme Court observed:

It appears to us that the raising some slogans only a couple of times by the two lonesome appellants, which neither evoked any response nor any reaction from any one in the public can neither attract the provisions of Section 124A or of Section 153A IPC. Some more overt act was required to bring home the charge to the two appellants, who are Government servants. The police officials exhibited lack of maturity and more of sensitivity in arresting the appellants for raising the slogans- which arrest -and not the casual raising of one or two slogans -could have created a law and order situation, keeping in view the tense situation prevailing on the date of assassination of Smt. Indira Gandhi. In situations like that, over sensitiveness some times is counter productive and can result in inviting trouble. Raising of some lonesome slogans, a couple of times by two individuals, without anything more, did not constitute any threat to the Government of India as by law established nor could the same give rise to feelings of enmity or hatred among different

⁵⁰ AIR 1960 SC 633

communities or religious or other groups.”⁵¹

Similarly, the Supreme Court in *Hindutva* judgement made curious distinction between asking vote on ‘caste, creed and religion base’ and ‘making a Hindu state’ which is not a religion but a ‘way of life’.⁵² It is submitted that such an interpretation may be catastrophic to the nascent democracy where illiterate or semi-literate voters may not be in position to reflect the intention, howsoever good that may be, of election candidate. It would be better to save in entirety the basic values of different sections of society and put an end to every such attempt.

International Perspective of Hate Speech

Both the ICERD and the ICCPR prohibit hate speech. The ICERD goes as far as requiring states to criminalize hate speech.⁵³ These two treaties demonstrate the growing concern of the international community with the prevention and prohibition of hate speech.

‘Any advocacy of national, racial, or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence shall be prohibited by law.’⁵⁴ That pronouncement of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), counts among the strongest condemnations of hate speech. It has been in force now for thirty years, alongside other international norms. It now represents as a norm of customary law, which would mean that states would be responsible in international law for banning at least some forms of hate speech even if they are not parties to the ICCPR or other instruments containing similar norms.

About 170 nations are parties to the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (ICERD),⁵⁵ demonstrating the international community’s sweeping support to the treaty. It is main tool for the international community to combat racial discrimination. Having universal reach, it is legally binding, and it has self-implementation tools. It prohibits hate speech in the form of propaganda that incites racial discrimination.⁵⁶ It goes beyond the hate speech prohibition⁵⁷ in the International Covenant on Civil and Political

⁵¹ *Superintendent Central Prison v Ram Manohar Lohia* AIR 1960 SC 633

⁵² *Manohar Joshi v Nitin Bhaurao Patil* (1996) 1 SCC 169

⁵³ ICERD Article 4

⁵⁴ Article 20(2) of ICCPR 1966

⁵⁵ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, Ratifications and Reservations, available on <http://www.ohchr.org/english/countries/ratification/2.html> visited at date 15/01/08

⁵⁶ Article 4 of ICERD 1966

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

Rights (ICCPR) and mandates for the state parties to criminalize hate speech.⁵⁸ The broad support for the treaty demonstrates the commitment of international community to the criminalization of hate speech.⁵⁹

The ICCPR prohibits advocacy of racial and national hatred when it constitutes an incitement to discrimination.⁶⁰ About 150 countries are parties to the ICCPR, none of whom object to Article 20(2),⁶¹ demonstrating the international community's strong support to the prohibition of hate speech.

The International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) decided *Prosecutor v. Nahimana, Barayagwiza, & Ngeze*, a case that explicitly states that prohibition of hate speech has become CIL.⁶² The ICTR, after examining well-established principles of international and domestic law and international and domestic cases, found that "hate speech that expresses discrimination violates the norm of customary international law prohibiting discrimination."⁶³ The ICTR's decision reflects the position of the international community. The United Nations Security Council created the ICTR, which demonstrates the ICTR is an organ backed by the international community. This influential international organ has spoken about hate speech prohibition as a matter of CIL. This is further support that the Hagan Committee's holding is justified by an arising CIL prohibiting hate speech.

⁵⁸ Article 4 of ICERD states in part:

States Parties condemn all propaganda and all organizations which are based on ideas or theories of superiority of one race or group of persons of one colour or ethnic origin, or which attempt to justify or promote racial hatred and discrimination in any form, and undertake to adopt immediate and positive measures designed to eradicate all incitement to, or acts of, such discrimination and, to this end...:

(a) Shall declare an offence punishable by law all dissemination of ideas based on racial superiority or hatred, incitement to racial discrimination. . . .

International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination article 4, opened for signature Mar. 7, 1966, 5 I.L.M. 352, 660 U.N.T.S. 195 (entered into force Jan. 4, 1969) [hereinafter ICERD].

⁵⁹ *Ibid*

⁶⁰ Article 20(2) states: "Any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility to violence shall be prohibited by law." International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; adopted Dec. 19, 1966, 6 I.L.M. 368, 999 U.N.T.S. 171. Hereinafter referred as ICCPR

⁶¹ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, Ratifications and Reservations available at <http://www.ohchr.org/english/countries/ratification/4.html> visited on Feb. 27, 2005

⁶² *Prosecutor v Nahimana, Barayagwiza, & Ngeze*, Case No. ICTR-99-52-T, Judgment and Sentence, 1076, Dec. 3 2003: <http://65.18.216.88/default.html>

⁶³ *Id.*

United States of America and Hate Speech

The United States' approach is to balance the right to free speech with prohibitions of hate speech. Freedom of speech, one of the most respected constitutional guarantees, is also "one of America's foremost cultural symbols." Unlike other Western nations, where hate speech is prohibited entirely, the American approach may in fact allow some types of hate speech under the protection of freedom of speech.

In United States hate crime is defined as an offence in which the victim is targeted because of the actual or perceived race, colour, religion, disability, sexual orientation, or national origin of that victim. This definition is based on Federal legislations that defined hate crime as an offence "that manifests evidence of prejudice based on race, religion, disability, sexual orientation, or ethnicity"⁶⁴ or more recently, as a crime in which "the defendant intentionally selects a victim, because of the actual or perceived race, colour, religion, national origin, ethnicity, gender, disability or sexual orientation of any person".⁶⁵ On the basis of the legal definition, most researchers on hate crime tend to conceptualize hate crime as a manifestation of inter-group conflict or violence as motivated by the distinctiveness of the victim(s), because the offender only targets victims with different group memberships.

American approach to prohibition of hate speech seems to be attenuating. This approach reflects the constant conflict between freedom of speech and protection against discrimination. In *R.A.V. v. City of St. Paul*,⁶⁶ the Supreme Court struck down a city ordinance prohibiting cross-burning that is intended to "arouse anger, alarm or resentment in others on the basis of race, color, creed, religion or gender." The Court held that the ordinance was impermissibly selective in its application of the ordinance; that it only applied to fighting words that insult or provoke violence on the basis of race, colour, creed, religion or gender."⁶⁷ By implication, fighting words used in connection with other ideas, such as hostility based on political affiliation, are not covered. The Court's holding in this case seems to indicate the United States is more committed to freedom of speech, to the detriment of hate speech law.

A subsequent case, however, seems to modify this position. The Supreme Court has indicated that the legislature may regulate certain

⁶⁴ Hate Crime Statistics Act, 1990

⁶⁵ Violent Crime Control and Law Enforcement Act of 1994 (Public Law 103-322, H.R. 3355).

⁶⁶ 505 U.S. 377 (1992)

⁶⁷ *Id.* at 391

types of speech, including certain hate speech. In *Virginia v Black*⁶⁷ the Supreme Court gave new hope to anti-hate speech law proponents. The Court in Virginia found that cross burnings performed on someone's lawn is a form of unprotected intimidation rather than protected speech. Virginia allowed hope for proponents of hate speech regulation that was not thought possible after the R.A.V. holding. The Supreme Court's move from R.A.V. to Virginia shows that, even in a nation where freedom of speech is held as one of the most sacred Constitutional guarantees, hate speech law is a rising concern.

Conclusion

Hate crime and consequential hate speech attacks the victim not only physically but also at the very core of his or her identity, causing a heightened sense of vulnerability beyond that normally found in other crime victims. The hate-motivated violence carries with it the clear message that the target and his group are of marginal value. The impact of hate crimes reaches beyond the harm done to the immediate victim or victims of the criminal behaviour. There is a widespread impact on the "target community" that shares the *Group characteristic* of the victim and an even broader based harm to the general society. Members of the *target community* do more than sympathizing or even empathizing with the immediate hate crime victim and perceive such crime as if it was an attack on them directed by themselves.

Finally, the impact of hate crimes may spread well beyond the immediate victims and the target community to the general society. Such crimes violate not only society's general concern for the security of its members and their property but also the shared value of equality among its citizens and racial and religious harmony in a multicultural society.

The pluralism is the strength of our country. This pluralism is very much reflected in various provisions of the Constitution particularly in Articles 14 and 25. Hate speeches are generally used for pseudo-domination or some time an attempt to overshadow the other's religion and culture. Any such act or attempt needs to be criminalized to protect the diversity of culture which makes this country a distinct place on the Earth. It is well established that no fundamental right is absolute including 19(1)(a). Freedom of speech and expression cannot be interpreted to include any such speeches, consequences of which can be mass scale violence and hatred in the society.

⁶⁷ 538 U.S. 343 (2003)

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